

DOI:

Digital Financial Literacy Among Working Women of Chitwan District, Nepal

Sujata Kumari Sharma^{1*}, Dipendra Silwal²¹BBA Scholar, Oxford College of Engineering and Management, Gaidakot, Nepal²Faculty of Computer Application, Oxford College of Engineering and Management, Gaidakot, Nepal*Corresponding email: suzusharma91@gmail.com

*ORCID: 0009-0005-7390-120X

Abstract

Nepal is under rapid digitalization, with major leaps in financial services. Fundamental digital financial literacy is of paramount importance for individuals, particularly working women, to effectively participate in the economic landscape. Mobile banking, digital wallets, QR-based payments are turning into new norms in life. It is very important that, in such a scenario, women should be empowered with these skills to reduce gender disparities while contributing to general economic empowerment in a region like Chitwan District. This research study aimed to assess the digital financial literacy among working women in Chitwan District, Nepal. It also focuses on the knowledge, usage patterns, difficulties, and suggestions by the respondents for the improvement of their adoption and security.

A quantitative research design was employed, with primary data collected through structured questionnaires from 150 working women across sectors including education, healthcare, agriculture, business. High awareness and adoption were evident, with 96.3% of respondents using digital tools like mobile banking, digital wallets, or QR payments, mainly for bill payments, online shopping, and transfers. However, barriers included high service charges, fear of fraud, limited smartphone/internet access, and technical knowledge gaps. While 94.4% knew security practices, 25.9% had experienced fraud, and 20.4% lacked confidence. Recommendations focused on training programs, awareness campaigns, and affordable technology.

Empowering women's digital financial literacy leads to high confidence and economic inclusion. Addressing these challenges will foster a secure, gender-responsive digital financial ecosystem in Nepal, ensuring sustainable development and equity.

Keywords: *digital financial literacy, financial inclusion, mobile banking, working women*